

4. D. N. POPOV, *Chem. Abs.*, 1933, **27**, 357.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry", Part III, Longmans, London, 1958 p. 679.
6. A. CHRZASZCZEWSKA, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 212.
7. J. VEGER and C. PERLIN, *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **66**, 79665.
8. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", 5th ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1956, p. 334.
9. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", 5th ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1956, p. 224.
10. N. D. CHERONIS, J. B. ENTRIKIN and E. M. HODNETT, "Semi Micro Qualitative Organic Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 728.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium with Pyrimidine-2-thiols

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SEVERAL pyrimidine-2-thiols have been found to be promising chromogenic reagents for osmium and other platinum metals by Singh and coworkers¹⁻⁴. In continuation of these studies osmium-complexes of 1-propyl (I) – and 1-(6'-amino-5'-hydroxy-3'-mercaptopyrimidyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H-pyrimidine-2-thiols (II) have been investigated spectrophotometrically. They are suitable for photometric determination of metal in micro-amounts. The results are reported in the present paper.

Experimental

Osmium(VIII) solution was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of OsO₄ (Johnson Mathey, England) in 0.2N sodium hydroxide. The solution was standardised iodometrically⁵. Pyrimidine-2-thiols were synthesised by the method of Mathes⁶. 0.01M solutions of these thiols were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of I in 0.02M hydrochloric acid and II in methanol. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade and doubly distilled water was used through out the studies. Unicam, SP-600, spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements. Elico pH-meter, model LI-10, was used for pH measurements.

Procedure for Determination of Osmium with Thiol I :

To a suitable aliquot of solution containing 55 to 205 μg of osmium, add 1-2 ml of 5N hydrochloric acid and 4-5 ml of 0.01M solution of thiol I. Dilute the solution to 10 ml and set aside for 1 hr or heat for about 10 min. on a steam bath. Add 10 ml of *n*-butanol and shake for about 15 min. on an electric shaker. Separate organic layer, centrifuge and measure its absorbance at 510 nm against *n*-butanol blank. Deduce the osmium content from calibration curve.

Procedure for Determination of Osmium with Thiol II :

To osmium solution (containing 20-170 μg of metal), add 3-4 ml of 0.01M solution of thiol II in methanol and adjust pH of the solution in the range 4.5-8.0, using dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide. Heat the solution for about 10 min. or keep aside for 45 min. Dilute it to 10 ml, keeping 50% methanolic medium (v/v). Measure the absorbance at 520 nm against 50% aqueous methanol blank and deduce metal content from precalibrated graph.

Results and Discussion

Osmium(VIII) reacts with colourless solutions of thiols I and II, in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid and in neutral or weakly acidic medium respectively. Reactions are slow at room temperature and take 1 hr. and 30 min. for completion with thiol I and II respectively. Alternatively 10 min. heating on a steam bath is also sufficient for full colour development with both the thiols. The complexes thus formed do not dissociate appreciably in 24 hr. The order of addition of various reagents does not affect the colour development in both cases. These thiols do not form coloured complexes on reaction with Os(IV), but a similar one with Os(VI). This indicates that in their osmium-complexes the oxidation state of metal is probably six and reduction with thiol takes place. Characteristics of osmium-complexes and optimum conditions for determination are as follows :

Osmium-1-propyl-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H,4H-pyrimidine-2-thiol (I) Complex :

Red coloured osmium-thiol I complex, having metal and ligand in 1 : 2 ratio, is extractable in several common organic solvents but the best results are obtained with *n*-butanol. Shaking for about 15 min. on an electric shaker is required for complete extraction. The complex absorbs maximum at 510 nm (ϵ 8200 l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹). Full colour development takes place in the presence of 0.5-3.5N hydrochloric acid and 15-times molar excess of thiol. Sulphuric, nitric and perchloric acids are equally good for this purpose. The system obeys

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Beer's law up to 25 ppm of osmium. Optimum concentration range for determination is 5.5 to 20.5 ppm of metal. Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is found to be $0.0225 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$.

Osmium-1-(6'-amino-5'-hydroxy-3'-mercaptopyrimidyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H, 4H-pyrimidine-2-thiol (II) Complex :

Osmium-thiol II complex (λ_{max} 520 nm ; ϵ 14600 $1 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is unextractable in common organic solvents and have been studied in 50% methanolic medium (Thiol precipitates at lower methanol concentration). Its absorbance remains maximum and constant in between pH 4.5 and 8.0. To adjust pH the dilute solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide are used because no buffer is found suitable for this purpose. At least 25-times molar excess of thiol II is required for maximum complexation. Beer's law is obeyed upto 19 ppm of osmium. Optimum concentration range for determination and Sandell's sensitivity have been found to be 2-17 ppm and $0.013 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ respectively. Job's and Bent and French methods have shown that metal to ligand ratio in the complex is 2 : 3.

Effect of Diverse ions :

Determination of 10 ppm of osmium has been attempted in presence of foreign ions. $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SCN^- , I^- , CN^- and thiourea interfere seriously in both cases. Tolerance limits (ppm) for other ions are recorded below in parentheses.

Os-thiol I Complex :

F^- or Br^- (4000) ; NO_3^- (2000) ; SO_4^{2-} or $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (4000) ; NO_2^- (25), tartrate (5000) ; citrate (4000) ; EDTA (1000), Cu^{2+} (10), Ag^+ (15), Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} or Ni^{2+} (20) ; Zn^{2+} (60) ; Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} (20) ; Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} (80) ; Sn^{2+} (40) ; Al^{3+} (60) ; Cr^{3+} (10) ; V^{4+} (5) ; Pd^{2+} (5) ; Ir^{3+} (40) ; Ru^{3+} (20) ; Rh^{3+} (40) ; Pt^{4+} (20) ; Au^{3+} (10).

Os-thiol II Complex :

F^- or Br^- (3000) ; NO_3^- (1000) ; NO_2^- (20) ; SO_4^{2-} (2000) ; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (3000) ; citrate (2000) ; tartrate (3000) ; EDTA (500) ; Ag^+ (5) ; Cu^{2+} (10) ; Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} or Ni^{2+} (10) ; Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} (40) ; Zn^{2+} (40) ; Cd^{2+} or Hg^{2+} (20) ; Sn^{2+} (20) ; Al^{3+} (30) ; Cr^{3+} (10) ; V^{4+} (2) ; Pd^{2+} (5) ; Ru^{3+} (10) ; Rh^{3+} or Ir^{3+} (20) ; Pt^{4+} (10) ; Au^{3+} (5).

Same tolerance limits for diverse ions are observed when several ions are present together provided appropriate reagent excess is used. To further increase the selectivity of these reagents, attempts have been made to mask some of the cations. In the determination of 10 ppm of osmium with thiol I, the tolerance limits in the presence of masking agents are ; 500 of Fe^{3+} , 200 of Al^{3+} and 100 of Cr^{3+} in presence of F^- ; 400 of Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+}

and Ba^{2+} in presence of SO_4^{2-} ; 350 of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cd^{2+} and Cu^{2+} in presence of citrate or tartrate ; 200 of Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Cd^{2+} in presence of EDTA and 50 of V^{4+} in presence of tartrate. In the determination with thiol II, 300 ppm of Fe^{3+} , 100 ppm of Al^{3+} and Cr^{3+} can be masked with fluoride. At least 200 ppm of Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} can be tolerated with SO_4^{2-} . Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Cd^{2+} and Cu^{2+} can coexist up to 200 ppm in presence of citrate or tartrate and up to 100 ppm in presence of EDTA. Attempts to mask other cations were unsuccessful in the case of both the reagents.

Composition of Thiols I and II as Reagents for Osmium :

Thiol II is more sensitive for osmium than I. This may be attributed to the greater molecular weight of thiol II and its bidentate character whereas thiol I behaves most probably as a monodentate ligand. From selectivity point of view, thiol I is slightly better than thiol II. This is perhaps due to the use of extractive procedure in the case of former.

Comparison with other well known reagents^{5,7} for osmium has revealed that these thiols are comparable in sensitivity but better in selectivity. At least equal amounts of all other platinum metals do not interfere in the determination. Moreover, these reagents are also free from rigid control over working conditions which is a necessity with various well known reagents.

Comparison with other pyrimidine-2-thiols^{1,2}, investigated for the determination of osmium, reveals that replacement of simple alkyl or aryl groups^{1,2} ('R' in the structure) with 6-amino-5-hydroxy-3-mercaptopyrimidyl group doubles the sensitivity keeping the selectivity level almost the same.

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References

1. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL, R. P. SINGH and N. K. RALHAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 851.
2. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 650.
3. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1978, **23**, 1153.
4. DEVLINA NATH, A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 457.
5. F. E. BEAMISH, *The Analytical Chemistry of the Noble Metals*, Pergamon Press, London, 1966.
6. R. A. MATHES, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1747.
7. F. E. BEAMISH and J. C. VONLOON, *Recent Advances in Chemistry of the Noble Metals*, Pergamon Press, London 1972.